

The Photo-reduction of Alcoholic Solutions of Ferric Chloride.

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Ferric salts are reduced when their solutions in aqueous solution of some organic substances or in non-aqueous solvents are exposed to light. The photochemical reduction of the aqueous solutions of ferric chloride has been observed by Benrath (*Annalen*, 1911, 382, 222) in presence of aldehydes and by Ghosh and Purakayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 827) in presence of some organic acids.

Benrath (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1905, 72,ii, 220) has also found that the density of solutions of ferric chloride in methyl and ethyl alcohols changes during exposure to sunlight and to artificial light and from the ratio of the change in density to the time of exposure he has concluded that the reduction of ferric chloride in alcoholic solutions is a photochemical one. Puxeddu and Vodret (*Gazzetta*, 1922, 52, i, 229) have found that the photo-reduction of ferric chloride in ethereal solution follows, up to a certain stage, the equation for monomolecular reactions.

In the following, the photo-reduction of alcoholic solutions of ferric chloride has been studied and the effect of (a) intensity of incident light and of small amounts of water, (b) temperature and (c) neutral electrolytes on the photo-reduction has been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL.

(a) *The Effect of the Intensity of Light and of Small Amounts of Water.*

A 1000-watt Philips lamp was used as the source of light and its intensity was kept constant by means of an adjustable resistance.

Two parallel beams of light obtained from the source were passed through cells containing 4 cm. thick column of distilled water to cut off the heat radiations. The intensity of light of one of the beams was diminished by interposing piles of glass plates in the path of the beam and it was measured by means of a Ruben's thermopile connected to a Broca galvanometer.

The alcohols used were Kahlbaum's or Merck's extra pure chemicals. Ethyl and *n*-amyl alcohols were perfectly anhydrous and *n*-propyl and *n*-butyl alcohols contained traces of water. B. D. H.-A. R. ferric chloride was used.

Solution of ferric chloride was introduced into each of the two identical cells of internal dimensions 20 mm. \times 50 mm. The cells were closed by well-fitting rubber stoppers carrying two syphon tubes provided with rubber tubings and pinch-cocks at the outer ends to prevent access of air. The stoppers were made perfectly airtight by coating them with methylated collodion.

The cells were then exposed to light for a certain time at room temperature (29-30°). To ensure optical homogeneity during exposure, the solution was occasionally gently shaken, as done by Ghosh and Purakayastha (*loc. cit.*), and this was found to give reproducible results. Stirring the solution with an inert gas could not be employed, because of the considerable removal of the alcohol caused thereby.

The exposed solution was then transferred to a bottle closed airtight by a rubber cork carrying burettes containing standard solutions of sodium thiosulphate and iodine respectively, so that no air came into contact with the solution. The amount of reduction was determined by adding excess of the thiosulphate solution to the exposed solution and titrating back the excess with the solution of iodine.

The results obtained by this method are comparable amongst themselves. But a maximum difference of 2% was noticed between these results and those obtained, using potassium dichromate in presence of phosphoric acid.

In the following tables, symbols x_1 and x_2 denote the millimoles of ferric chloride reduced, for the intensities I_1 and I_2 , respectively, of the light incident on the cells; the intensities are given in cm. of the galvanometer deflections.

The values of k_1 and k_2 , the unimolecular constants for the photo-reduction of ferric chloride, have been calculated wherever possible.

TABLE I.

Solution in Ethyl Alcohol.

$$I_1 = 23.0 \text{ cm.} \quad I_2 = 5.6 \text{ cm.}$$

(a) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.174 M.

<i>T</i> (hrs.)	...	1	2	3	4	5
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	12.17	19.50	24.3 ₃	24.33	22.05
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	10.70	19.10	24.13	21.36	24.65

(b) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.174 M + 0.5 c.c. water.

<i>T</i> (hrs.)	...	$\frac{1}{2}$	1	2	3
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	17.15	18.40	18.60	16.30
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	14.84	21.50	18.90	15.59

(c) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.066 M.

<i>T</i> (hrs.)	...	2	3	4	5
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	2.40	6.80	8.11	10.63
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	1.00	3.75	4.65	4.86

(d) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.066 M + 0.5 c.c. water.

<i>T</i> (hrs.)	...	1	2	3	4	5
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	4.10	7.70	8.18	3.40	4.00
$k_2 \times 10^3$...	4.76	5.24	3.80		

TABLE II.

Solution in n-Propyl Alcohol.

$$I_1 = 23.0 \text{ cm.} \quad I_2 = 9.0 \text{ cm.}$$

(a) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.176 M.

<i>T</i> (hrs.)	...	1	2	3	4	5
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	27.60	26.80	23.70	22.55	20.00
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	23.30	26.20	25.50	22.80	22.30

(b) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.088 M.

<i>T</i> (hrs.)	...	1	2	3	4
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	13.70	15.50	14.50	15.35
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	6.40	12.68	12.10	11.90
		$k_1 = 0.0132;$	$k_2 = 0.0064.$		

TABLE III.

Solution in n-Butyl Alcohol. $I_1 = 24$ cm. $I_2 = 5.9$ cm.

(a) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.14 M.

T (hrs.)	...	$\frac{1}{2}$	1	$1\frac{1}{2}$	2	3
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	5.96	12.80	11.70	9.75	8.10
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	4.50	13.80	11.06	9.40	7.80

(b) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.0672 M.

T (hrs.)	...	1	$1\frac{1}{2}$	2	3
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	4.75	6.50	7.30	11.05
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	1.15	2.42	4.20	6.63

TABLE IV.

Solution in n-Amyl Alcohol. $I_1 = 22.45$ cm. $I_2 = 14.75$ cm.

(a) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.236 M.

T (hrs.)	...	1	2	3	4	5	6
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	10.50	15.56	27.88	36.22	40.87	44.16
$k_2 \times 10^3$...	3.27	3.39	3.55	3.97	3.93	3.83

Mean 3.66

(b) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.236 M + 0.5 c.c. water.

T (hrs.)	...	1	$1\frac{1}{2}$	2	3	4
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	24.00	—	37.23	36.50	33.42
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	21.13	31.44	44.31	37.36	27.65

(c) Solution exposed: 2.5 c.c. of 0.0637 M.

T (hrs.)	...	1	2	3	4	5
$x_1 \times 10^2$...	8.72	10.58	6.15	6.60	6.07
$x_2 \times 10^2$...	6.37	7.50	7.00	5.47	4.12

 $k_1 = 0.0112$; $k_2 = 0.0069$.

It will be seen that the intensity of the incident radiation has less effect on the velocity of the photo reduction of concentrated solutions of ferric chloride than on the weaker ones.

By plotting the values of x and T , it will be seen that something like a stationary state is reached in the photo-reduction of solutions of ferric chloride in anhydrous alcohols; the equilibrium is set up earlier in the concentrated solutions than in the dilute ones. The addition of water both to the concentrated and to the dilute solutions accelerates the reduction of ferric chloride in the beginning but with the progress of the reaction, apparently the reverse reaction is more accelerated than the direct one. This is indicated by a maximum point in the (x, T) curves for these solutions. A complete reversal, however, never takes place.

Van Alphen (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1930, 49, 754) has found that when a solution of ferric chloride in ethyl alcohol is heated in sealed tubes at 160° under high pressure, a reversible thermal reaction takes place. The reaction is accelerated when hydrated ferric chloride is used but the addition of larger amount of water retards the reaction.

The reduction of ferric chloride is almost zero-molecular in the concentrated solutions but it tends to become unimolecular in the weaker ones, especially in presence of water. The order of the reaction depends both upon the concentration of the solution and upon the intensity of the incident light.

(b) *The Effect of Temperature.*—Temperature coefficients of alcoholic solutions of ferric chloride for 10° rise were measured between 30° and 40° . A glass-fronted air thermostat was used and the temperature was kept constant within $\pm 0.2^\circ$. The reaction cell was properly screened from the bulb heater and the same arrangement of light was used as described previously. The results obtained are given in the following tables in which x_{30} and x_{40} represent millimoles of ferric chloride reduced at the temperatures 30° and 40° respectively and r , the temperature coefficient for 10° rise, *i.e.*, the ratio of $x_{40} : x_{30}$.

TABLE V.

Solution in Methyl Alcohol.

Conc. of $\text{FeCl}_3 = 0.08034 M.$				Conc. of $\text{FeCl}_3 = 0.1992 M.$			
T (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2.$	$x_{30} \times 10^2.$	$r.$	T (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2.$	$x_{30} \times 10^2.$	$r.$
1	3.31	3.05	1.085	1	4.6	4.1	1.122
2	—	4.00	—	2	8.0	7.1	1.127
3	4.78	4.82	0.992	3	8.4	4.9	1.063
			Mean 1.0385				Mean 1.104

TABLE VI.

Solution in Ethyl Alcohol.

Conc. of FeCl ₃ = 0.1008 M.				Conc. of FeCl ₃ = 0.192 M.			
<i>T</i> (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2$.	$x_{30} \times 10^2$.	τ .	<i>T</i> (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2$.	$x_{30} \times 10^2$.	τ .
1	2.0	2.0	1.00	1	5.80	4.4	1.318
2	2.5	2.6	1.00	2	6.32	6.4	0.986
3	3.07	3.1	1.00	3	8.19	8.0	1.125
			Mean 1.00				Mean 1.143

TABLE VII.

Solution in n-Propyl Alcohol.

Conc. of FeCl ₃ = 0.092 M.				Conc. of FeCl ₃ = 0.1772 M.			
<i>T</i> (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2$.	$x_{30} \times 10^2$.	τ .	<i>T</i> (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2$.	$x_{30} \times 10^2$.	τ .
1	1.60	1.80	0.888	1	1.91	1.45	1.317
2	2.01	2.05	0.980	2	1.55	1.50	1.033
3	2.30	2.33	0.978	3	2.20	2.00	1.100
			Mean 0.948				Mean 1.150

TABLE VIII.

Solution in n-Butyl Alcohol.

Conc. of FeCl ₃ = 0.0824 M.				Conc. of FeCl ₃ = 0.225 M.			
<i>T</i> (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2$.	$x_{30} \times 10^2$.	τ .	<i>T</i> (hrs.).	$x_{40} \times 10^2$.	$x_{30} \times 10^2$.	τ .
1	0.95	1.00	0.95	$\frac{1}{2}$	4.45	4.40	1.010
2	1.48	1.32	1.12	1	9.22	8.9	1.036
3	2.10	2.10	1.00	1 $\frac{1}{2}$	12.50	12.90	0.969
			Mean 1.023	2	—	17.63	—
							Mean 1.005

The temperature coefficients of the photo-reduction of ferric chloride in alcoholic solutions for 10° rise are between 1.0 and 1.15 and they appear to be little affected by the change in the concentration of the solutions. This value of the temperature coefficient is nearly the same as that (1.01) obtained by Berthelot (*Compt. rend.*, 1915, 160, 440) for the reduction of ferric chloride by oxalic acid

The temperature coefficient for a number of photochemical halogen reactions has been found by a number of workers to be greater than unity. But in the majority of the photochemical reactions involving the decomposition of a molecule containing a

halogen, the temperature coefficient is nearly unity. Thus the temperature coefficients of the decomposition of hydrogen iodide (Bodenstein and Lieneweg, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 119, 123), of NOCl (Kiss, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1923, 42, 665), of NH₃ (Kühn, *compt. rend.*, 1924, 178, 708) and of Cl₂O (Bodenstein and Kistiakovsky, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 116, 371) were found to be nearly unity. In view of these data, it may be inferred that the primary reaction in the photo-reduction of ferric chloride in alcoholic solutions is the breaking up of the ferric chloride molecules into those of ferrous chloride and chlorine.

(c) *The Effect of Neutral Electrolytes.*—To study the effect of electrolytes, different volumes of known solutions of the electrolytes in alcohols were added to the same volume of the alcoholic solutions of ferric chloride and the total volume of the mixture was made the same in each case. The concentrations of the electrolytes were small enough not to introduce any appreciable alteration in the absorption of light. The results obtained are given in the following tables, in which *E* represents the equivalents of the electrolytes present in one litre of the reaction mixture and *x*, millimoles of ferric chloride reduced. The period of exposure of solutions was one hour in all cases and the intensity of light falling on the solution was kept at the same value during each exposure.

TABLE IX.

0.1868M-FeCl₃ solution in Methyl Alcohol.
With no electrolyte, $x \times 10^2 = 4.50$.

Electrolyte.	<i>E</i> .	$x \times 10^2$.	% Velocity of reaction
NaCl	0.017	2.46	54.67
	0.034	1.10	24.45
	0.051	0.43	9.56
KCl	0.005	2.25	50.00
	0.010	0.90	20.00
	0.015	0.30	6.66
LiCl	0.050	2.90	64.45
	0.100	0.00	0.00
MgCl ₂	0.017	2.10	46.66
	0.034	0.00	0.00

TABLE X.

0.305 M-FeCl₃ solution in Ethyl Alcohol.
With no electrolyte, $x \times 10^2 = 14.2$.

Electrolyte.	<i>E</i> .	$x \times 10^2$	% Velocity of reaction.
NaCl	0.0255	13.10	92.23
	0.034	12.20	85.91
KCl	0.005	12.90	90.84
	0.010	12.81	86.68
LiCl	0.050	13.26	93.38
	0.100	12.40	87.33
MgCl ₂	0.017	13.10	92.23
	0.034	12.40	87.33

TABLE XII.

0.211 M-FeCl₃ solution in
n-Propyl Alcohol.

With no electrolyte, $x \times 10^2 = 5.42$.

Electrolyte.	E.	$x \times 10^2$.	% Velocity of reaction.
NaCl	0.017	3.47	64.02
	0.034	2.32	42.80
KCl	0.005	4.12	76.03
	0.010	3.78	69.74
LiCl	0.050	3.12	57.56
	0.100	1.92	35.42
MgCl ₂	0.017	4.32	79.70
	0.034	4.42	81.55

TABLE XI.

0.115 M-FeCl₃ solution in
n-Butyl Alcohol.

With no electrolyte, $x \times 10^2 = 1.16$.

Electrolyte.	E.	$x \times 10^2$.	% Velocity of reaction.
NaCl	0.017	0.55	47.41
	0.034	0.60	51.72
KCl	0.005	0.90	77.50
	0.075	0.50	43.10
LiCl	0.050	0.67	57.75
	0.075	0.40	34.47
MgCl ₂	0.017	0.46	39.60
	0.034	0.26	22.41

The results indicate that the photo-reduction of ferric chloride is inhibited by the addition of small quantities of the electrolytes and the inhibition is greater, the larger the amount of the electrolyte added.

Berger (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1921, **40**, 387; *ibid.*, 1925, **44**, 47) has found that neutral electrolytes have a catalytic effect on many photochemical reactions and it is primarily brought about by a change in the electrostatic forces within the solution. On the basis of the effect of electrolytes, he has classified the photochemical reactions into three groups: (i) those that are very sensitive to the presence of electrolytes, (ii) those in which the inhibition, noticeable at low concentrations, becomes pronounced at higher concentrations, and (iii) those in which even the highest concentration of electrolytes do not affect the velocity of reaction by more than a few per cent.

The photo-reduction of ferric chloride in alcoholic solutions probably belongs to the second group of reactions.

Summary.

1. The intensity of incident light has less effect on the velocity of photo-reduction of the comparatively concentrated solutions than on the dilute ones.

2. The reaction appears to reach a stationary state in solutions in perfectly anhydrous alcohols.

3. The addition of water accelerates the direct reaction for sometime but afterwards the reverse reaction is more accelerated than the direct one.

4. The temperature coefficients for 10° rise between 30° and 40° lie between 1.00 and 1.15.

5. The addition of minute quantities of sodium chloride, lithium chloride and magnesium chloride has an inhibitive effect.

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